

PROXIMATE AND ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES OF COMPLEMENTARY FOOD MADE FROM SORGHUM AND DEFATTED GROUNDNUT FLOUR ENRICHED WITH DATE PALM FLOUR AND TAMARIND

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Abstract

The production of complementary foods from sorghum and defatted groundnut flours enriched with date palm and tamarind flour was locally processed into five ratios. Groundnut paste porridge served as the control. Proximate composition and organoleptic parameters were assessed using the standard method for proximate composition and the 9-point hedonic scale for organoleptic properties. Results showed that the defatted groundnut complementary porridge had an average mean value for protein (10.40 % to 13.25 %), fat (2.50 % to 3.77 %), fiber (0.15 % to 0.20 %), ash (6.20 % to 7.50 %), moisture (62.60 % to 68.15 %), and carbohydrate content (13.03 % to 1.14 %) in an increasing order or mean in all the samples. The results of organoleptic properties showed a mean score value from the lowest to the highest, where textural properties ranged from 7.44 to 8.78, taste from 7.59 to 8.67, color attribute from 6.47 to 8.33, flavor from 7.26 to 7.96, and general acceptability from 7.30 to 8.89. SDCDT was the most preferred parameter among all the parameters evaluated. The nutrient density of the defatted groundnut complementary porridge was the highest compared with that of the control SGT sample. The organoleptic properties evaluated showed high scores in the defatted groundnut porridge sample compared with the control and most preferred. It also showed economic benefits where the extracted oil could be used for other purposes. As a consequence, the use of defatted groundnut in porridge making could be encouraged and thus adopted by food scientist, dietitians, nutritionists and other health care practitioners in their dietary prescriptions and interventions.

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INTRODUCTION

Complementary feeding refers to the progressive introduction of nutrient-containing foods or liquids to a child's diet while continuing to breast-feed (Agostoni *et al.*, 2008). The production of low-cost, high-energy food products for infants receiving complementary foods is a constant challenge. This is particularly important in developing countries where malnutrition remains a major concern. Complementary foods should have sufficient energy and nutrients to meet the needs of infants (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020).

Porridge is made of grains, such as oats, quinoa, barley, farro, or wild rice, cooked in liquids, such as water, milk, or milk alternatives (Welch, 2017). The grains are cooked until they start breaking down and releasing their starch; using ground, rolled, pearled, or cracked grains helps speed up the lengthy cook time for making porridge (Othman *et al.*, 2011). It is a food made by heating or boiling ground, crushed, or chopped starchy plants, typically grain, in milk or water. It is often cooked or served with added flavorings, such as sugar, honey, fruit, or syrup, to make a sweet cereal, or it can be mixed with spices, meat, or vegetables to make a savory dish (WHO, 2020). It is usually served hot in a bowl, depending on its consistency. The term "porridge" is used in Britain specifically for oat porridge (oatmeal). This is a hot mixture of oatmeal or oats slowly cooked in water or milk. It is typically eaten for breakfast alone or with salt, sugar, fruit, milk, cream, or butter, and sometimes with other flavorings. Groundnut paste is a common mixture or addition in the preparation of porridge, which enhances its nutritional value and is practiced in many parts of Africa, including Nigeria. Rice, wheat, barley, corn, guinea corn, triticale, and buckwheat are other grains used for porridge. Many types of porridge have their own names, such as congee (rice), polenta (maize), and poi (from Taro) (Othman *et al.*, 2011).

The recommended amount of energy required from complementary foods is obtained by subtracting the amount of energy provided by breast milk from the average recommended energy need (Brown, 2017). Since milk requires a fairly broad range of energy, the energy from complementary foods is estimated for children receiving low, medium, and high amounts of energy from breast milk. The stomach capacity, which is approximately 30 g/kg body weight (WHO, 2020), the health status of the children, and the frequency of meals should all be considered (Agostoni *et al.*, 2008). It is not possible to develop estimates of the minimally adequate energy density of complementary foods without simultaneously considering the feeding frequency. Increasing the number of meals per day can satisfy the energy requirements of diets with lower energy density.

According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) (2003) recommendations, the transition from exclusive breastfeeding and/or infant formula feeding to complementary feeding, referred to as complementary feeding, typically covers the period from 6 to 24 months of age and is a very vulnerable period (WHO, 2020). The vulnerable period in question refers to the period when malnutrition starts in many infants, which significantly contributes to the high prevalence of malnutrition in children aged 5 years worldwide and affects subsequent optimal development (Adinsi *et al.*, 2014). In developing countries like Nigeria, malnutrition during the complementary feeding period is mainly attributed to low-nutrient dense foods, which are given to children as weaning foods. This study aimed to produce porridge from sorghum, groundnut, date palm, and tamarind. Hence, the proximate composition and organoleptic parameters of the products were determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used in this study

The following materials are used in the preparation of complementary food: sorghum, groundnut, date palm, coconut, and tamarind at different proportions.

Sources of raw materials

The raw material/ingredients used in this research article were purchased from Mubi North main market, Adamawa State, Nigeria. Each raw material was packaged separately in polythene bags and then transported to the processing laboratory before the preparation of the complementary foods.

Table 1: Research design

Samples	Sorghum (%)	Groundnut (%)	Defatted groundnut (%)	Date palm (%)	Coconut (%)	Tamarinds (%)
SGT	60	30				10
SDT	60		30			10
SDDT	50		30	15		5
SDCT	50		30		15	5
SDCDT	40		25	15	15	5

Keys

SGT = sorghum flour (60 %), groundnut paste (30 %), and tamarind (10 %); SDT = sorghum flour (60 %), defatted groundnut cake flour (30 %), and tamarind (10 %); SDDT = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %), date palm (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); SDCT = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %), coconut (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); SDCDT = sorghum flour (40 %), defatted groundnut flour (25 %), coconut (15 %), date palm (15 %), and tamarind (5 %).

Sample Preparation

The whole raw materials obtained, such as sorghum, groundnut, date palm, coconut, and tamarind, were semi-processed in the Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics food formulation unit, Federal Polytechnic Mubi, Nigeria, following Aggarwal and Verma (2008). Analysis of the samples was carried out in the Animal Nutrition Laboratory, Adamawa University Mubi.

Production of Various Formulations

The complementary porridge was produced according to the following ratio: Where five (5) samples produced using different formulation ratios of millet, groundnut paste, defatted groundnut cake, coconut milk, and tamarinds. Two hundred milliliters (200 mL) of clean water was allowed to boil in a stainless steel pot using a gas cooker (Hungarian Maxi 5050 4B Rapid Gas cooker). Sorghum flour (60%, 60%) was mixed into a slurry along with a groundnut paste (30%), which was also mixed in the dissolved sorghum flour and thoroughly mixed into a fine consistency following a similar method described by Angelo *et al.* (2023). The solution was poured into boiling water with constant stirring to maintain a fine consistency while cooking. This was allowed for about 10 min, after which 10 g of tamarind was added. When tamarind was added, the porridge was set with its thickening effect and flavoring characteristics being noticed and thus removed from the cooker. The method was adopted for the preparation of complementary porridge enriched with coconut milk following the formulation ratio outlined in the research design (Zhang, 2022).

ANALYSIS METHODS

Determination of the Proximate Composition

The proximate composition (moisture, crude protein, crude fat, ash, crude fiber, and carbohydrate content and energy value) of the samples was determined using the standard methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists, (2005). The moisture content was determined using an air oven at 105 °C for 3 h. Crude protein was determined using the micro-Kjeldahl method (Method No 978.04), and crude fat was determined using the Soxhlet extraction method (Method No 2003.06). The ash content was determined by ashing the sample in a muffle furnace (Gallenkamp 3) at 550 °C for 4 h (Method No. 942.05), while crude fiber was determined by

Contemporary Journal of Advancement in Food Science and Technology Vol. 12 (2) Method No. 958.06. The total carbohydrate content was obtained by difference, and the gross energy of the samples was determined using a Gallenkamp ballistic bomb calorimeter.

Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties of the complementary porridge samples were evaluated for texture, taste, color, flavor, and overall acceptability. Organoleptic parameter evaluations were performed using the 9-point hedonic scale measures for the 5 samples by 27 untrained panelists randomly selected among staff and adult students of the Department of Human Nutrition, Nutrition and Dietetics, and Food Science Technology (Brestensky *et al.*, 2012).

Statistical Analysis

The raw data obtained were expressed as (mean \pm SD) (standard deviation) of triplicate measurements for proximate composition and 27 measurements for organoleptic attributes. The data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Statistical Product of Service Solution Version 22.0 software, and the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) method was used to compare the means of the experimental data at 95 % confidence interval.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate composition (%) of complementary porridge produced from sorghum, groundnuts, coconuts, date palm, and Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*) blends

The results for protein in Table 1 showed a significant difference across all samples. The highest protein content was found in sample SDDCT (13.25 %), whereas the lowest was found in the control sample SGT (10.40 %). The higher values obtained across the samples with defatted groundnut could be attributed to the nutrient density of the defatted groundnut used compared with the usual groundnut paste used in the complementary formulation of porridge, which has the lowest value. Enrichment with dates and coconut enhances the nutrient composition of the products. WHO/FAO/UNU (2007) stipulates that 0.83 g/kg body weight per day could be expected to meet the requirements of almost 97.5 % of healthy individuals. The formulations, especially the defatted groundnut porridge, provide a good amount of protein to meet child requirements for healthy growth and development.

The carbohydrate content of the five samples differed significantly across all samples. The highest carbohydrate content was found in SDDCT (17.14 %), while the lowest was found in SGT (13.25 %), which served as the control. Angelo *et al.* (2023) reported higher values for carbohydrate across developed extruded complementary porridge diet where defatted groundnut paste was used compared with that of the groundnut paste. Carbohydrates serve as a source of energy for all bodily functions, particularly brain functions, and are necessary for the metabolism of other nutrients (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Values for all samples show an appreciable amount of carbohydrate for the growth, development, and energy requirements of children.

The fat content of the five samples showed values ranging from 3.76 % to 2.50 % as the highest and lowest for SDDCT and SGT samples, respectively. According to Angelo *et al.*, (2023), the low fat content of porridges could be attributable to the high viscosity of complementary porridges, which requires a large amount of water to obtain the right consistency for the child, thereby displacing the nutrient density of the porridge (Meeks-Gardner *et al.*, 2020). The slight difference in fat content could be attributed to the deep frying of the paste to obtain a dried product in the form of groundnut cake. Deep frying also causes a substantial amount of water to escape from the product while absorbing some fats. According to Kris-Etherton *et al.* (2008), fat is a concentrated source of energy, and its presence in these porridges can contribute to the overall energy content of the diet and is important for nutrient absorption and hormone synthesis. WHO recommends 30-35 % of the total energy should be allotted to fat. Infants and children up to 2 years of age should consume approximately 40 % of their energy from fat (Wardlaw, 2010).

Crude fiber content shows no significant difference across samples SDT, SDDT, SDCT, and SDCDT with a result of 0.20 %, but significantly different with sample SGT, which is the control, with a result of 0.15 %. This could also be attributable to the defatted groundnut's nutrient density used in the formulations compared to the control where the groundnut paste was used. The judicious combination of ingredients consisting of dates, coconuts, and sorghum in the complementary diet could also be a factor in the slightly higher percentage of the developed products' fiber content. The result corresponds with similar findings conducted by Angelo *et al.* (2023), in which the created products with defatted groundnut had a higher percentage of fiber content compared to the one that had groundnut paste. Fiber is important for digestive health and can contribute to a feeling of fullness, aiding in weight management (Slavin, 2013).

According to Jenkins *et al.* (2019), fiber also helps in regulating digestion, promoting a feeling of fullness and bowl emptying, and reducing the risk of several chronic diseases, including heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and colorectal cancer. Low-fiber content can be augmented with feeding frequency and, consequently, the supply of its dietary and health benefits to the child.

The ash content shows appreciable values across all five samples, ranging from 7.50 % for the SDCDT sample, while the SGT and SDDT samples had the lowest content at 6.20 %. These appreciable ash values could be attributed to the combination of ingredients, including sorghum, groundnut, dates, coconut, and tamarind, in the complementary porridge diet. This corresponds to the findings of Angelo *et al.* (2023), where higher percentages of values were obtained in products with a combination of defatted groundnuts compared to the one with the usual groundnut paste. Ash is a measure of inorganic mineral elements present in foods that contribute to the overall nutritional value of diets (Gropper *et al.*, 2017).

The moisture content of the five (5) samples showed a values ranging from 68.15% to 62.60 % due to the high bulk density of cereal-based porridge and their failure to meet the WHO estimated needs from complementary foods (WHO, 2020). Moreover, composite flour usually made of cereal and legume combinations is a good match for a balanced amino acid diet (El Hassan *et al.*, 2008; Davidson, 2014). The high moisture content of the sample could also imply that it is a diet taken at a warm temperature enough to be tolerated by the infant.

The complementary diet compared favorably with and even more in terms of nutritional value, as evidenced in the results. Thus, it is undervalued for not being used for children aged 6–24 months. Enrichment of defatted groundnut with dates and coconut increases its nutritional value compared with the normal groundnut paste product. Consequently, it should be encouraged to be incorporated in the diet, especially for children aged 6–24 months.

Table 1: Proximate composition of the five (5) diets/formulations (%)

Sample	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Fiber (%)	Ash (%)	Moisture (%)	Carbohydrate (%)
SGT	10.40 ± 0.00 ^e	2.50 ± 0.00 ^c	0.15 ± 0.00 ^b	6.20 ± 0.00 ^e	67.50 ± 0.00 ^a	13.25 ± 0.00 ^e
SDT	12.40 ± 0.00 ^b	3.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.20 ± 0.00 ^a	7.00 ± 0.00 ^d	62.60 ± 0.00 ^c	15.40 ± 0.00 ^a
SDDT	10.86 ± 0.01 ^d	2.70 ± 0.00 ^c	0.20 ± 0.00 ^a	6.20 ± 0.00 ^e	66.00 ± 0.00 ^b	13.45 ± 0.00 ^b
SDCT	11.65 ± 0.00 ^c	2.60 ± 0.00 ^d	0.20 ± 0.00 ^a	7.00 ± 0.00 ^d	65.60 ± 0.00 ^b	13.03 ± 0.04 ^d
SDCDT	13.25 ± 0.00 ^a	3.77 ± 0.01 ^a	0.20 ± 0.00 ^a	7.50 ± 0.00 ^c	68.15 ± 0.00 ^a	17.14 ± 0.01 ^c

Values are presented as means of duplicate analysis ± standard deviation. Values with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $P < 0.05$).

Keys

SGT = sorghum flour (60%), groundnut paste (30%), and tamarind (10 %); **SDT** = sorghum flour (60 %), defatted groundnut cake flour (30 %), and tamarind (10 %); **SDDT** = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %), date palm (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); **SDCT** = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %),

Contemporary Journal of Advancement in Food Science and Technology Vol. 12 (2) coconut (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); **SDCDT** = sorghum flour (40 %), defatted groundnut flour (25 %), coconut (15 %), date palm (15 %), and tamarind (5 %).

Evaluation of Organoleptic Parameters of Porridges Produced from Sorghum, Groundnut, Date Palm, Coconut, and Tamarind

The textural attributes of the complementary porridge across all samples show favorable acceptance among the panelists. Samples SDT, SDCT, and SDD showed no significant difference among them, with the highest scores of 8.52, 8.78, and 8.78, respectively. Samples SGT and SDCDT had the lowest score at 7.44 for both. Taste evaluations showed no significant difference across 3 samples having the highest scores of liked very much, namely sample SDCT, SDDT, and SDCDT, at 8.78, 8.58, and 8.44, respectively. These higher scores for the taste of these products could be attributable to the enrichment of the product with dates and coconut, thereby adding to the taste compared to the complementary diets.

Color evaluation shows sample SDDT getting the highest scores of liked very much at 8.33. Sample SDCT and SDCDT with moderately liked at 7.02 and 7.15, respectively. The higher scores by the panelist for the developed product could be attributable to the enrichment of the products with dates and coconut compared to sample SGT, which is the usual groundnut paste porridge with slight liking.

Flavor evaluation for all samples shows no significant difference across all samples with moderately liked ratings scores. The panelist’s general acceptability ratings show the enriched products with dates and coconut, these are samples SDCT, SDDT, and SDCDT, showing no significant difference among them and having the highest scores of liked very much. These results could be attributed to the enrichment of the products with dates and coconut, implying that enrichment influenced the organoleptic parameters in the ratings compared with the usual groundnut paste porridge and defatted groundnut that were not enriched with dates and coconut. The developed products received the highest ratings compared with those that were not enriched. This implies that the panelists accept and approve the dates and coconuts used in the developed products.

Table 2: Evaluation of organoleptic parameters of porridges produced from sorghum, groundnut, date palm, coconut, and tamarind

Codes	Texture	Taste	Color	Flavor	General acceptability
SGT	7.44±1.95 ^b	7.59±1.80 ^a	6.46±1.913 ^b	7.96±2.278 ^a	7.52±2.208 ^a
SDT	8.52±1.78 ^a	7.63±2.35 ^a	7.48±2.343 ^a	7.67±2.11 ^a	7.30±2.44 ^a
SDDT	8.78±1.368 ^{ab}	8.67±1.861 ^b	7.02±2.165 ^c	7.41±2.135 ^a	8.74±1.430 ^b
SDCT	8.58±1.649 ^{ab}	8.52±1.847 ^b	8.33±1.441 ^d	7.26±1.933 ^a	8.59±1.824 ^b
SDCDT	7.44±1.95 ^b	8.26±1.196 ^b	7.15±1.68 ^c	7.96±1.698 ^a	8.89±1.847 ^b

Values are presented as means of 27 measurement *mean* ± *SD* standard deviation. Values with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different P < 0.05).

Keys

SGT = sorghum flour (60 %), groundnut paste (30 %), and tamarind (10%); SDT = sorghum flour (60 %), defatted groundnut cake flour (30 %), and tamarind (10 %); SDDT = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %), date palm (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); SDCT = sorghum flour (50 %), defatted groundnut flour (30 %), coconut (15 %), and tamarind (5 %); SDCDT =

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the proximate and organoleptic properties of the complementary porridge formulated from a blend of sorghum, groundnut paste, de-fatted groundnut cake, date palm, coconut milk, and tamarinds were analyzed. These local ingredients are innovative tools used to increase the nutrient density of the complementary porridge with higher nutritional value and consumer acceptability compared with the control sample made from

Contemporary Journal of Advancement in Food Science and Technology Vol. 12 (2) conventional materials such as sorghum, groundnut paste, and tamarinds. Thus, the production and promotion of this complementary diet with defatted groundnut cake flour or its paste should be encouraged and adopted. Incorporation of dates palm and coconut adds a lot to its nutrient density, which could be beneficial in combating malnutrition among the populace, and highly recommended for dietitians and other health care practitioners.

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